

OPTIMIZATION MULTI-OBJECTIVE PARALLEL MULTI-WORKSHOP FLOW-SHOP SCHEDULING PROBLEM UNDER NO-WAITING CONSTRAINT

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ABSTRACT: *Currently, a novel generalization of the flow-shop scheduling issue within a multi-workshop setting is raising increasing apprehension among the operational research community. In this article, we concentrate on a system seldom seen in the literature, which is made up of three identical workshops installed in parallel. A specific issue of scheduling in parallel flow-shop multi-workshop environments with no waiting constraint (No-Wait PFSSP) is examined. Two combined objective functions need to be minimized: the just-in-time (the sum of the averages of advance and delay) and the makespan. The drawback commonly faced in this kind of workshop is the uneven distribution of workloads among various workshops. Consequently, a load balancing phase among the various workshops was incorporated into the optimization procedures. For the analysis of this issue, three optimization meta-heuristics are proposed: Genetic Algorithm (GA), Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO), and Ant Colony Optimization (ACO). To assess the significance of the results obtained and the effectiveness of the proposed algorithms, numerous tests have been conducted. The findings indicated that PSO is the most effective algorithm, demonstrating high success rates, consistent performance, and robust optimization, thus making it ideal for real-world applications in time-sensitive sectors. GA obtained moderate outcomes, particularly in minor cases. It demanded additional computation time, which restricted efficacy in bigger scenarios. While quick and effective regarding CPU usage, the algorithm (PSO) exhibits greater variability and diminished reliability.*

KEYWORDS: *scheduling, Meta-heuristic, parallel flow shop, without waiting, load balancing.*

1 INTRODUCTION

In the contemporary era, artificial intelligence has become an essential tool. The integration of this tool into the production system plays a crucial role in a smart factory. Smart production should include production, scheduling, logistics and cooperation between companies. M. R. Garey & al. (1979) Indeed, the problem of scheduling the production system has become increasingly complicated due to the rapid development of techniques, manufacturing equipment and customer demands. The transition from single-line to multi-line manufacturing was made easier by the parallel flow shop scheduling problem (PFSSP). The PFSSP problem has thus become a particularly dynamic and fruitful research area, due to its increasingly intensive use in industry. The parallel production system multi-workshop, allows to obtain a high-quality production and other advantages, such as reduction of production costs,

production delays, management risks, etc. This problem can be referred to a special hybridization of parallel machine scheduling (PMS) and flow-shop scheduling (FSSP), when a number of parallel flow shops are used to process a set of parallel jobs in order to optimize one (or more) scheduling criteria. Figure 1 shows an illustrative example of the flow shop workshops in parallel, each consisting of m consecutive machines.

Pang & al. (1999), H. Wang & al. (2017) proposed the method of kinematic design and control for the CCPGT. A CCPGT can be applied to drive a mechanism at a non-uniform speed. This kind of mechanism is called a variable speed input mechanism. And it was seldom investigated before 1990. S. Hatami & al. (2018), firstly presented a novel approach to improve the state of the motion of the follower by varying the input speed using a servomotor. After that, K. Allali & al (2022), T. Bousonville (2002) contributed to improving the

output motion characteristics of a mechanism by a servomotor solution. Although the method is effective, there are still some disadvantages that exist due to the utilization of a servo motor, for instance, higher cost, a specially designed servomotor required, slow response, and limited output power. A new way to drive the variable speed input mechanism is an open topic to be investigated.

Fig. 1 An illustration of a parallel multi work-shop production system.

In industry, there are two configurations of parallel multi-workshops. In the first, products run through separate parallel workshops without common resources, Pang & al. (1999), H. Wang & al. (2017), S. Hatami & al. (2018), K. Allali & al. (2022). As for the second, the products go through parallel workshops, necessarily passing through one or more common resources. T. Bousonville (2002), X. Zhang & al. (2012), F. G. Guimaraes & al. (2016).

The no-wait scheduling problem (NWFSP) is one of the crucial variants of the processing shop scheduling problem, where no waiting time is allowed between successive operations of each task. For technological reasons, once a job/product has started on the first machine, it must be continued until it is finished on the last machine without any intervention on or between machines. The imposition of shop constraints is common in various industries such as food processing, N. G. Hall & al. (1996), Y. Wang & al. (2018), transportation, C. Mannino & al. (2009), J. Kim & al. (2009), chemical products, and surgery Y. Wang & al. (2015), pharmaceutical manufacturing, hydrocarbons, etc.

The flow shop scheduling problems are NP-complete because of their combinatorial optimization character. This complexity becomes NP-hard for flow-shop scheduling problems of parallel workshops with more than three machines or two lines and more M. R. Garey & al. (1979) and because of the constraint of no-waiting. It is therefore crucial to develop effective methods for solving these complex scheduling problems. The high complexity of PFSSP makes methods accurate, such as, whole programming H. M. Wagner (1959), and the Branch and Bound S. Kouki & al. (2011). Not practical for large instances. This is the main reason

why literature offers various approaches such as heuristics and metaheuristics.

In this paper, we have treated the problem of parallel scheduling multi-shop flow-shop under no-waiting constraint. We examined the case of separate parallel multi-workshops without common resources. Most works encountered in the literature take into consideration a single objective function, P. Sundararaghavan & al. (1997), H. Bargaoui & al. (2016), P. Devapriya & al. (2016), W. Shao & al. (2017). In order to get closer to the reality of the production system, we took into consideration two objective functions: minimization of total working time (makespan), which means the maximum time needed to complete all work, and just-in-time, which is to say minimization of the sum of advance and delay tasks. These objectives have a direct impact on delivery times, which improves production efficiency and customer satisfaction. However, these objectives are generally in conflict, which makes it difficult to optimize one without harming the other, hence the importance of multi-optimization methodologies Objective to balance conflicting objectives and achieve more resilient and effective outcomes. In addition, the implementation of constraints, such as the requirement for no waiting, in other words, with stock zeros between machines of the same workshop, requires that consecutive tasks be carried out without pause. This constraint increases the complexity of scheduling processes. Previous studies have thoroughly investigated the impact of this constraint on scheduling tactics.

To obtain acceptable-quality solutions within a reasonable time, we focused on metaheuristic approaches. In this context, we propose tree metaheuristic algorithms based on aggregation techniques, genetic algorithms (GA), particle swarm optimization (PSO) and ant colony optimization (ACO).

Finally, following several experiments, it was found that the direct use of algorithms on parallel multi-workshop scheduling problems gives solutions but with lines loaded and others underloaded, which is detrimental to the optimal result. To solve this problem, we have integrated a load balancing module into the metaheuristics flow chart, which gives better solutions and more balanced workshops. The results obtained are really promising.

Thus, the main contributions of this work are: (i) the realistic extension of the optimization problem from an objective function to multi-objective optimization by introducing aggregated methods. (ii) most of the works related to our work, presented in the literature, are limited to two parallel workshops formed by two machines each and generally set as an objective the minimization of the Makespan and few

of them deal with the multi-objective case. This article is distinguished by the study of the multi-objective case under the no-waiting constraint of jobs between machines and (iii) the development and integration of a load balancing technique between the different parallel workshops.

The other sections of this document are structured as follows: Section 2 provides an overview of related work. Section 3 illustrates the description of the problem and the corresponding mathematical model. Section 4 focuses on resolution approaches. Section 5 presents and discusses the results achieved. Section 6 provides a conclusion and future outlook.

2 RELATED WORKS ANALYSIS

The traditional production systems have shifted from being single-site to decentralized multisite systems due to globalization. The Flow Shop scheduling problem has become a pioneer in producing easier and faster programs and sequences of operations with pre-determined resources and this is achieved through the exchange of information between resources, factories, jobs and machines which formed the parallel flow-shop scheduling problem (PFSSP), Parallel Flow Line, scheduling in multi-factory and the distributed flow-shop scheduling problem (DFSSP). Automation has become an integral part of practical manufacturing systems today. In this part, we examine some research connected to the issue at hand. Nevertheless, various tasks with varied designations are associated with our issue.

2.1 Parallel Flow Line Scheduling Problem (PFLSP)

PFLSP involves organizing and overseeing workflows in a manufacturing setting that utilizes several parallel processing lines to produce goods. This strategy strives to enhance efficiency in production, reduce delays, and ensure resource utilization aligns with demand. It requires a careful balance of systematic planning, resource allocation, and flexible response to demand and capacity changes. S. Rajendran & al. (2015) utilized the genetic algorithm for reducing the makespan in parallel flow-line scheduling. They used a method that involved generating a group of random solutions for random samples, then applying crossing and mutation operators to enhance the solutions until reaching a satisfactory fitness level. S. Rajendran & al. (2016), suggested to explore the near optimal sequences based on heuristic algorithms with the objective to minimize Makespan. Metaheuristic method of swarm intelligence based on bee colony algorithm are proposed. Computational results show

that GA based algorithm outperforms ABC in all instances of the chosen problem sets.

2.2 Multi-Factory Scheduling Problem (MFSP)

Scheduling in MFSP requires coordinating and optimizing production activities in various manufacturing sites to maximize efficiency, cut costs, and fulfill customer orders. This kind of scheduling is especially crucial in supply chain management and operations management for companies with multiple factories producing similar or different products. multi-factory scheduling requires an understanding of production processes to optimize output across all facilities. The goal is to create a system that meets customer demand while minimizing costs and maximizing resource utilization. J. Behnamian & al. (2021) studied multi-objective scheduling in the production network in which each factory has its customers and demands can be satisfied by itself or other factories and assumed that jobs can transfer from the overloaded machine in the origin factory to the factory, which has fewer workloads by imposing some transportation times. For simultaneous minimization of the sum of the earliness and tardiness of jobs and total completion time, the scheduling problem are modeled as a mixed-integer linear program, the existing multi-objective techniques are analyzed. Since this problem is NP-hard, a heuristic algorithm is also proposed to generate a set of Pareto optimal solutions. H. Kazemi & al. (2024) investigated a new multi-factory configuration in which distinct factories produce different final product components in the first stage. Each factory is considered as a classical flow-shop, which can manufacture a unique component. These components are assembled into final products in the assembly factory, which is located in the second stage. in the intent of research is to schedule the jobs in each factory to minimize the makespan of the entire process. For this purpose, a mixed-integer programming model is developed to deal with small-size instances. Furthermore, to deal with larger instances, five heuristic methods are developed, and the worst-case analysis is carried out. Y. Chen & al. (2023) proposed a bi-objective model of multi-factory production scheduling to optimize the trade-off between the on-time delivery performance and the total operating cost of the single batch of export orders. The transport plan and the long shipment lead time are considered in the proposed model.

2.3 Distributed Flow-shop Scheduling Problem (DFSSP)

In the DFSSP, a set of n unrelated jobs are processed in F factories. A factory should be selected for processing each job. Each factory is equipped with a set of m machines. The DFSSP was first studied by David et al. (1996) to model a glass industry with immediate processing and batch production. T Mraïhi & al. (2024) they reviewed academic literature on the Distributed Permutation Flow shop Scheduling Problem and Flow Shop with worker flexibility to classify and identify how human factors have an important role in workshop scheduling. Furthermore, they presented the Distributed Permutation Flow Shop scheduling problem with worker flexibility. V. F. Viagas & al. (2018) addressed the distributed permutation flowshop scheduling problem to minimize the total flowtime. They focused on approximate procedures, and propose eighteen constructive heuristics to obtain high-quality solutions in reasonable CPU times. In addition, they proposed an iterative improvement algorithm to further refine the so-obtained solutions. P. P. Gonzalez & al. (2024) carried out a review of the DFSSP literature aimed at providing a classification and notation for DFSSP problems under a common framework. The contributions are exhaustively presented and discussed. T. Meng & al. (2019) they introduced the customer order constraint into the DPFSP. In this problem, a set of customer orders need to be manufactured in a number of factories and each order composed of some defined jobs should be processed in the same factory. The objective is to minimize makespan among factories. They presented three heuristics exploring three rules for generating the seed job sequence as well as two rules for assigning orders to factories. Besides, they developed three meta-heuristics, namely, a variable neighborhood descent (ORVND), an artificial bee colony (ORABC) and an iterated greedy (ORIG). C. Gogos (2023) approached using Constraint Programming and its specialized scheduling features, such as interval variables and non-overlap constraints, while a novel heuristic is proposed for computing lower bounds. Two constraint programming models are proposed: the Distributed Permutation Flow-shop Scheduling problem, and that drops the constraint of processing jobs under the same order for all machines of each factory. Finally, they demonstrated the great benefits of scheduling problems that stem from using state-of-the-art constraint programming solvers and models that capture the problem tightly. K. Mousighichi & al. (2024) they addressed study of the distributed permutation flow shop scheduling problem with no-idle and due window constraints.

The aim is to determine the job assignments to the factories and their sequences in each factory that provide the minimum total weighted earliness and tardiness penalties considering due windows. They offered four different mathematical models, and presents a benchmark to examine different problem cases that may arise in practical applications. Two hybrid metaheuristic algorithms based on the Iterated Greedy are proposed. These metaheuristics exhibit promising capabilities.

2.4 Parallel flow Shops Scheduling Problem (PFSSP)

In many real-world manufacturing applications, a number of parallel flow shops are often used to process the jobs. The scheduling problem in this parallel flow shop system has gained an increasing concern from the operational research community, however, multiple scheduling criteria are rarely considered simultaneously in the literature. P. S. Sundararaghavan & al. (1997) analyzed a specific instance of parallel flow workshop issues (known as the parallel processor problem) in order to reduce the makespan. They created and verified heuristic and simulation methods for tackling complex issues, and also utilized precise techniques for smaller issues. T. Qi & al. (2014) They studied the typical scheduling problem of PFSSP, which is characterized by multi-product, multi-stage, parallel equipment. This article introduces a heuristic different algorithm (HDA) that uses continuous codes to represent batch size at each stage in order to improve the particle's ability to manage constraints. Q. Tang (2015) studied the PFSSP, which is characterized by multi-product, multi-stage, parallel production, production coordination between stages, limit of equipment production capacity and inventory capacity, parallel equipment selection and limitation of batch quantity, and modified quantum evolutionary algorithm (MQEA) with continuous codes representing the batch size on the every stage is presented, to enhance the ability to handle constraints. The findings indicated that MQAE can deliver either optimal or near-optimal solutions efficiently for all areas in a brief timeframe. M. Mansouri & al. (2023) proposed a hybridization of two well-known optimization algorithms, a bio-inspired meta-heuristic PSO and a local search algorithm TS, with the aim of minimizing Makespan. The concept of the proposed method is to start by generating a set of near-optimal solutions by PSO algorithm. Then, the TS algorithm refines and improves these solutions in order to attain the optimal solution. H. Wang & al. (2017) examined a special parallel flowshop scheduling (PFSS) problem of two parallel non-identical shops, one with two consecutive machines and the other with only

one machine, is investigated with two objective functions of minimizing the total flow time of jobs and the number of tardy jobs in the two-machine flow shop. To solve PFSSP a multi-objective evolutionary algorithm (MOEA) based memetic algorithm hybridizing the local search technique into the framework of NSGA-II is proposed. S. Hatami & (2018) addressed the PFSSP with stochastic processing times, where a product composed of several components has to be finished at a particular moment. The processing time of each operation at each factory is a random variable following a given probability distribution. The aim is to find the robust starting time of the operations at each factory in a way that all the components of the product are completed on a given deadline with a user-defined probability. A simheuristic algorithm is proposed in order to minimize the makespan in the deterministic version and a makespan percentile in the stochastic version.

Most of the work related to our work, presented in the literature, is limited to two parallel flow shops each formed by two machines, and generally sets as an objective the minimization of the Makespan and few of them deals with the case of multi objective. To our knowledge the only work that is near to ours is that of W. Shao & al. (2019) which considers a multi-objective DFSSP no-wait with sequence-dependent setup time (MDNWFSP-SDST). The performance criteria are the makespan and the total weight tardiness. In the MDNWFSPSDST, several identical factories are considered with the related flow-shop scheduling problem with no-wait constraints. For solving the MDNWFSP-SDST, the algorithm (PEDA) is proposed. Three probabilistic models including the probability of jobs in empty factory, two jobs in the same factory, and the adjacent jobs are constructed. The PWQ heuristic is used to generate initial individuals. A sampling method with the referenced template is presented to generate offspring individuals. Several multi-objective neighbourhood search methods are developed to optimize the quality of solutions.

3 PROBLEM DEFINITION

3.1 Problem statement

The flow shop parallel workshop scheduling is a class of scheduling problems with a wide range of applications. In this type of problem, we are given a set of L flow shop workshops each of them is equipped with m machines assembled in series and a set of n tasks, each task consists of a set of m operations which must be processed on the machines of one of the workshops. The scheduling problem No-wait parallel flow shop noted $PF|No - wait|C_{max}, \sum(\alpha_i E_i + \beta_i T_i)$ may be described as

follows: assuming that n parts must be processed in L -parallel flow shop. Each job must be assigned to a single flow shop line, where the job in question must follow the entire production sequence. In this sequential processing scenario, each machine can only process one part at a time, and each of n tasks must pass through each of the machines in the flow shop line in question once in the same predefined order of passage, no preemption or interruption is allowed during production. To satisfy the constraints of non-waiting, once a part starts execution on the first machine, from a flow shop line the process of processing this task will be continuous on the following $m-1$ machines without waiting, c_{ijk} that is, the end date of the current task is equal to the start date of the next task. Thus, the start date of a job on the first machine could be delayed. This problem has major implications in multiprocessor industries, including steel processing, pharmaceutical, chemical, plastic, electronics and food industries. It also finds these applications in modern manufacturing systems, where robots and industrial machines implement highly coordinated processes. The processing times of tasks on machine are predefined. All tasks are available at time 0 (at the beginning of scheduling) and all machines are always available. The objective is to find a schedule that simultaneously minimizes the makespan (which is the maximum time for completion of work) and the lead time and delay.

3.2 Mathematical model

Notation:

i, j = index of jobs, $i, j = 1, 2, \dots, n$.

l = index of flow shops, $l = 1, 2, \dots, L$.

k = index of machines in a flow shop, $k = 1, 2, \dots, m$.

$p_{\pi_i k l}$ = processing time for k -th operation (on k -th machine) of job π_i in flow shop l .

$c_{\pi_i k l}$ = completion time for k -th operation of job π_i in flow shop l .

G = the biggest positive number.

d_{π_i} = due date of job π_i .

α_{π_i} = earliness penalty of job π_i per unit time early.

β_{π_i} = tardiness penalty of job π_i per unit time tardy.

E_{π_i} = earliness of job π_i .

T_{π_i} = tardiness of job i .

$X_{\pi_i k} = 1$ if job π_i is processed in flow shop k , and 0 otherwise

$Y_{\pi_i \pi_j k m} = 1$ if job π_i precedes job π_j on machine m in flow shop l , and 0 otherwise.

Pour faciliter la description, les notations sont répertoriées comme suit.

Set:

J : set of jobs, $J = \{J_1, J_2, \dots, J_n\}$ where n is the number of jobs.

M : set of machines in each flow shops, $M = \{M_1, M_2, \dots, M_m\}$. where m is the number of machines.

Q: set of parallel flow-shops, $Q = \{Q_1, Q_2, \dots, Q_L\}$, where q is the number of flow-shop.

Parameters:

$p_{\pi_i, k, l}$: the processing time of job π_i on the machine k in flow-shop l .

Variables:

$$x_{\pi_i, l} = \begin{cases} 1: & \text{if job } \pi_i \text{ is processed on flow shop } l \\ 0: & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$y_{\pi_i, \pi_j, k, l}$

$$= \begin{cases} 1: & \text{if job } \pi_i \text{ is processed more earlier than job } \pi_j \\ & \text{by machine } k \text{ on flow shop } l \\ 0: & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$C_{\pi_i, k, l}$: the completion time of job π_i on the machine k in flow-shop l .

The problem can be formulated as follows:

$$\min f = \min_{\pi \in \Pi} \left(\mu_1 \times \left(\max_{1 \leq l \leq L} (c_{\pi_n, l, m}) \right) + \mu_2 \times \left(\sum_{1 \leq i \leq n} (\alpha_{\pi_i} E_{\pi_i} + \beta_{\pi_i} T_{\pi_i}) \right) \right) \quad (1)$$

Subject to:

$$\sum_{1 \leq l \leq L} \sum_{1 \leq i \leq n} x_{\pi_i, l} = n \quad (2)$$

$$\sum_{1 \leq l \leq L} x_{\pi_i, l} = 1 \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, n \quad (3)$$

$$c_{\pi_1, k, l} = \sum_{1 \leq j \leq k} p_{\pi_1, j, l}; \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, m; l = 1, 2, \dots, L \quad (4)$$

$$c_{\pi_i, k, l} = c_{\pi_{(i-1), 1, l}} + \sum_{1 \leq j \leq k} p_{\pi_i, j, l} + \delta_{\pi_i}; \quad i = 2, 3, \dots, n; k = 1, 2, \dots, m; l = 1, 2, \dots, L \quad (5)$$

$$c_{\pi_1, k, l} = c_{\pi_1, (k-1), l} + p_{\pi_1, k, l}; \quad k = 2, 3, \dots, m; l = 1, 2, \dots, L \quad (6)$$

$$c_{\pi_i, 1, l} = (c_{\pi_{(i-1), 1, l}} + p_{\pi_i, 1, l}) x_{\pi_i, l}; \quad i = 2, 3, \dots, n; l = 1, 2, \dots, L \quad (7)$$

$$c_{\pi_i, k, l} = \left\{ \max \left(C_{\pi_{(i-1), k, l}}; C_{\pi_i, (k-1), l} \right) + p_{\pi_i, k, l} \right\} x_{\pi_i, l}; \quad i = 2, 3, \dots, n; k = 2, 3, \dots, m; l = 1, 2, \dots, L \quad (8)$$

$$c_{\pi_j, k, l} - c_{\pi_i, k, l} + \left(3 - x_{\pi_i, l} - x_{\pi_j, l} - y_{\pi_i, \pi_j, k, l} \right) \times S \geq p_{\pi_j, k, l} \quad i, j = 1, 2, \dots, n; k = 1, 2, \dots, m; l = 1, 2, \dots, L \quad (9)$$

$$c_{\pi_i, kl} - c_{\pi_j, kl} + \left(2 - x_{il} - x_{jl} - \mu_{ijkl} \right) \times G \geq p_{\pi_i, kl} \quad i, j = 1, 2, \dots, n; k = 1, 2, \dots, m; l = 1, 2, \dots, L \quad (10)$$

$$\sum_{1 \leq l \leq L} x_{il} (c_{\pi_i, (k+1), l} - c_{\pi_i, kl} - p_{i, (k+1), l}) \geq 0 \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, n; k = 1, 2, \dots, (m-1) \quad (11)$$

$$\delta_{\pi_i} = \max \left\{ 0; \max \left(c_{\pi_{(i-1), k, l}} - c_{\pi_{(i-1), 1, l}} - \sum_{1 \leq j \leq (k-1)} p_{\pi_i, j, l} \right) \right\}; \quad i = 2, 3, \dots, n; k = 2, 3, \dots, m; l = 1, 2, \dots, L \quad (12)$$

$$E_{\pi_i} = \max \left(0, \left(d_{\pi_i} - \sum_{1 \leq l \leq L} (c_{\pi_i, ml} x_{\pi_i, l}) \right) \right) \quad (13)$$

$$T_{\pi_i} = \max \left(0, \left(\sum_{1 \leq l \leq L} (c_{\pi_i, ml} x_{\pi_i, l}) - d_{\pi_i} \right) \right) \quad (14)$$

$$E_{\pi_i} \geq 0 \quad ; \quad i = \{1, 2, \dots, n\} \quad (15)$$

$$T_{\pi_i} \geq 0 \quad ; \quad i = \{1, 2, \dots, n\} \quad (16)$$

$$x_{ik} = \{0, 1\} \quad (17)$$

$$y_{ijkm} = \{0, 1\} \quad (18)$$

$$\mu_i \in [0, 1] \quad (19)$$

$$\sum_{1 \leq i \leq 2} \mu_i = 1 \quad (20)$$

Where, (1) the aggregate function formed by the combination of minimization of Makespan and the minimization sum of mean earliness cost and the tardiness cost (just-in-time. Constraint (2) denotes that all the jobs must be processed in the processing lines. Constraint (3) shows that each job can only be allocated to one processing line. Constraint (4), (5), (6), (7) and (8), denotes the completion time for all jobs, in each flow shop. (9) and (10) represent the sequence constraints for the different jobs in the same processing line and guarantee that one machine can only process one job as the same time. Constraint (11) describes that the operations of the same product must be processed on the machines of the same flow shop line, following the specific operating range of the product, and guarantees that a task cannot be processed only once by one only machine at a time. The no-wait characteristic of the problem ensures that the completion time difference between adjacent jobs is determined by the processing times of the two jobs, regardless of the other jobs in the permutation. Thus, a completion time distance can be defined between each pair of jobs. The completion time distance from job i to job j is calculated by (12). Constraint set (13) formulates the earliness of every job. Constraint set (14) formulates the tardiness of every job. Constraint (17) and constraint (18) state that the decision variables can take values of 0 or 1. Constraint sets (15), (16), (17), and (18) define the domain of the decision variables.

4 METHODS OF SOLUTION

In this paper, three algorithms: Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) algorithm, Genetic Algorithm (GA) and Ant Colony Optimization (ACO), were proposed to solve the optimization problem Multi-

Objective Parallel Multi-Work Shop Flow-Shop Scheduling Problem under No-No-Waiting Constraint. A load balancing module between the different ones has been integrated in each of the proposed algorithms, and we have also based on aggregation techniques during Multi-Objective optimization.

4.1 Genetic Algorithm (GA)

As shown in the pseudo-code figure (1), an AG is a parametric algorithm whose application to a given problem requires parameters to be defined and decisions to be made about how : define the coding of the problem, initial population is generated, parents are selected to produce children, selected parents are recombined, population size is adjusted, individuals are transferred or crossed and the likelihood of crossing and mutation probabilities that explore other areas of the research space.

4.2 Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) algorithm

PSO is an evolutionary algorithm to solve the optimization problem was proposed in 1995 by J. Kennedy & al. (1995). PSO soon became a very popular global optimizer, mainly in problems in which the decision variables are real numbers. The PSO is initialized with random positions (x_{ij}^t) and random particle velocity (v_{ij}^t). Then, it searches for the optimal global solution by adjusting the motion vector of each particle according to the best personal (cognitive) and global (social) positions of each particle at each iteration. Furthermore, a set of parameters is required: Inertia Weight (w), Cognitive constant (c1), Social constant (c2) and random vectors uniformly distributed (r1, r2) within the range [0,1].

$$v_i^{t+1} = wv_i^t + c_1r_1(P_{best_i}^{t+1} - x_i^t) + c_2r_2(g_{best}^{t+1} - x_i^t) \quad (21)$$

$$x_i^{t+1} = x_i^t + v_i^{t+1} \quad (22)$$

$$P_{best_i}^{t+1} = x_i^* | f(x_i^*) = \min_{1 \leq k \leq t} \{f(x_i^k)\} \quad i \in \{1, 2, \dots, N\} \quad (23)$$

$$g_{best}^t = x_*^t | f(x_*^t) = \min_{1 \leq i \leq N} \{f(x_i^t)\} \quad (24)$$

Ant Colony Optimization (ACO) algorithms

The Ant Colony Optimization (ACO) algorithm is a cooperative search metaheuristic based on the collective intelligence of a large number of artificial agents (ants) derived from the behavior of real ants. These agents are capable of building good solutions to difficult combinatorial optimization problems.

The ants cooperate in their search for food by depositing traces of pheromones (chemical substance) on the ground. Hence, the main idea of

ACO is to imitate the trail of pheromones used by real ants as a means of communication and feedback between them. The artificial pheromone is accumulated at execution by a learning mechanism. Artificial ants are implemented as parallel processes whose role is to construct problem solutions using a constructive procedure conducted by a combination of artificial pheromones, of problem data and an objective function used to evaluate successive constructive steps.

In the context of applying ACO algorithms to scheduling problems, with each iteration, pheromone values are updated. The pheromone τ_{ij} indicates the processing time of the work i in position j of a sequence is updated as follows:

$$\tau_{ij} = (1 - \rho) \cdot \tau_{ij} + \sum_{1 \leq k \leq m} \Delta\tau_{ij}^k \quad (25)$$

where ρ is the evaporation rate, m is the number of ants, and $\Delta\tau_{ij}^k$ is the amount of pheromone deposited on the edge (i, j) by ant k :

$$\Delta\tau_{ij}^k = \begin{cases} \frac{Q}{L_k} & \text{if ant } k \text{ used } \text{edg}(i, j) \text{ in its tour,} \\ 0 & \text{Otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (26)$$

where Q is a constant, and L_k is the length of the turn constructed by ant k .

In the construction of a solution, the ants select the next job to visit by a stochastic mechanism. When the ant k is in job i and has so far built partial solution s^p , the probability of joining job j is given by

$$p_{ij}^k = \begin{cases} \frac{\tau_{ij}^\alpha \cdot \rho_{ij}^\beta}{\sum_{v_{il} \in N(s^p)} \tau_{il}^\alpha \cdot \rho_{il}^\beta} & \text{if } v_{il} \in N(s^p), \\ 0 & \text{Otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (27)$$

where $N(s^p)$ is the set of possible components, i.e., the edges (i, l) where l is a job that has not yet been chosen by ant k . The parameters α and β control the relative importance of the pheromone in relation to the heuristic information η_{ij} , given by

$$\eta_{ij} = \frac{1}{d_{ij}} \quad (28)$$

where d_{ij} is the distance between job i and job j .

5 COMPUTATIONAL EXPERIMENTS

In order to evaluate the experimental performance of the proposed weighted aggregation algorithms like GA, PSO and ACO designed for No-Wait PFSSP, these were programmed with MATLAB. Simulations were performed on a PC with an Intel(R) Core (TM) i7-1355U @3.90 GHz processor and 32 GB of RAM under the Windows 10 operating system. It is important to note that the efficiency of the algorithm is strongly influenced by the number of machines, the volume of tasks, and the parameters of the algorithms. To measure the effectiveness of the algorithms, we performed a series of tests on a group of instances, in reference <https://github.com/chneau/go->

taillard/tree/master/instances, (consulted on 03/01/2025). These scenarios are mixtures of $n=\{20, 50, 100, 200, 500\}$ tasks and $m=\{5, 10, 20\}$ machines. There were 12 instance groups with 10 instances in each group, for a total of 120 instances. This implies that we must perform $10 \times 12 \times 3 \times 10 = 3600$ tests. The performance of algorithms is often influenced by the appropriate choice of their parameters. In this regard, the famous Taguchi method was applied, using three levels for each factor. Minitab software is used to design the experiments and analyze the results. Tables 1, 2, and 3 display the parameters and levels selected based on experience, and Figure 2 shows the results of the Taguchi method. For GA, the preferred values are population size; 80, selection type: Elitism, Crossover type: PMX, Crossover probability: 0.9, mutation type: CIM, and Mutation probability: 0.03. For PSO, the values are Swarm size; 80, Inertia Weight: 0.9, Cognitive Coefficient: 2, Social Coefficient: 2, Velocity Limits: ± 1 and additional parameters. For a fair comparison, for all algorithms, the maximum number of iterations is 100. For each experiment of an algorithm on a test instance, 30 independent runs are executed, and for all experiments, the best of 30 is chosen. The results of the run-time experiments, the makespan, as well as the advance and average delay, are recorded in tables for further analysis.

The proposed GA, PSO and ACO algorithm performance evaluation technique consist of relative percentage deviation (RPD) test obtained using formula (29) given by V. Fernandez-Viagas (2017):

$$RPD = \frac{z_i - z_{Best_i}}{z_{Best_i}} \times 100 \quad (29)$$

Where:

z_i = the value of the aggregate objective function of an algorithm used

z_{Best_i} = the best value of the objective function (makespan) of all the algorithms used

In this study, each dimension of the benchmark data consists of $R=10$ instances, so in summary the number of Average Relative Percentage Deviation (ARPD) [46]:

$$ARPD = \frac{1}{R} \sum_{1 \leq j \leq 10} RPD_j \quad (30)$$

One of the objectives is to balance loads between different workshops. Fig. 2 shows the Gantt diagram of 20 jobs ordered on three parallel workshops under no waiting constraints. The diagram is generated by the PSO algorithm by optimizing the sum of advance and delay penalties and makespan. Fig. 2 shows that the makespan of the workshops is very close to each other. This load balancing is further proved by the evolution of makespan, the three Work-shops of the

three proposed algorithms Fig. (3). Indeed, the makespan take a similar pace of evolution, where the values of the makespan of the Work-shops are very close to each other. This means that the costs are distributed evenly over the workshops.

Fig. 2 Gantt diagram of three work-shop

Table 1. Computational Results

Taillard's Instance	CPU				Agreggated function									RPD						
	PSO	GA	ACO	Best	PSO			GA			ACO			Best	CPU			Agreggated Function		
					WS1	WS2	WS3	WS1	WS2	WS3	WS1	WS2	WS3		PSO	GA	ACO	PSO	GA	ACO
Tai 01	0,231	0,239	0,241	0,231	180,50	172,50	179,25	184,00	186,50	176,50	178,75	170,50	181,50	176,92	0,000	3,404	4,241	0,282	2,971	0,000
Tai 02	0,267	0,256	0,249	0,249	200,25	211,75	215,50	198,00	206,75	200,25	198,00	210,00	203,00	201,67	6,768	2,803	0,000	3,586	0,000	0,982
Tai 03	0,246	0,256	0,258	0,246	176,75	180,00	190,50	170,25	171,25	205,50	162,50	174,50	202,50	179,83	0,000	3,747	4,593	1,416	1,371	0,000
Tai 04	0,269	0,251	0,249	0,249	199,25	196,50	184,75	199,00	185,50	194,75	194,75	202,25	186,25	193,08	7,430	0,801	0,000	0,215	0,000	0,686
Tai 05	0,251	0,262	0,259	0,251	182,00	220,75	206,50	179,00	209,00	186,75	209,00	198,75	169,50	191,58	0,000	4,420	3,297	5,663	0,000	0,433
Tai 06	0,253	0,243	0,249	0,243	155,25	213,75	189,00	171,00	204,75	195,25	175,50	192,50	197,25	186,00	4,123	0,000	2,629	0,000	2,277	1,283
Tai 07	0,273	0,283	0,272	0,272	196,25	189,25	193,75	203,50	180,75	182,75	207,50	179,00	179,50	188,67	0,094	3,674	0,000	2,287	0,176	0,000
Tai 08	0,269	0,284	0,281	0,269	204,25	197,25	183,00	206,75	200,25	187,75	206,00	204,00	186,75	194,83	0,000	5,223	4,443	0,000	1,723	2,053
20 × 05 Tai 09	0,270	0,278	0,265	0,265	221,00	222,25	173,25	204,00	202,25	187,00	206,25	224,75	181,50	197,75	1,801	4,442	0,000	3,771	0,000	3,143
Tai 10	0,272	0,265	0,270	0,265	152,00	183,75	195,75	152,00	199,00	193,25	195,25	194,50	168,25	177,17	2,876	0,000	2,131	0,000	2,343	4,749
Average	0,260	0,262	0,260	0,254	186,75	198,78	191,13	186,75	194,60	190,98	193,35	195,08	185,60	188,75	2,309	2,851	2,133	1,722	1,086	1,333
Tai 11	0,383	0,371	0,391	0,371	223,50	272,00	270,50	246,25	268,00	283,00	289,50	274,25	239,50	255,33	2,980	0,000	5,031	0,000	3,920	4,637
Tai 12	0,362	0,384	0,385	0,362	290,00	237,25	274,50	290,50	238,00	283,75	287,75	281,50	236,00	267,25	0,000	5,514	5,764	0,000	1,293	0,435
Tai 13	0,343	0,353	0,339	0,339	259,50	279,25	270,00	277,00	282,00	267,00	290,00	272,50	258,75	269,58	1,234	4,036	0,000	0,000	2,088	1,522
Tai 14	0,387	0,373	0,374	0,373	248,00	289,50	290,50	232,50	271,75	270,50	280,75	267,25	240,50	258,25	3,617	0,000	0,127	6,431	0,000	1,744
Tai 15	0,413	0,403	0,393	0,393	273,25	280,00	261,50	266,25	261,25	256,75	260,00	273,25	265,25	261,42	4,869	2,604	0,000	3,743	0,000	1,785
Tai 16	0,369	0,384	0,369	0,369	301,00	262,25	296,25	288,00	275,25	292,50	283,75	297,50	276,00	285,25	0,000	3,897	0,059	0,436	0,000	0,175
Tai 17	0,391	0,367	0,382	0,367	276,50	283,75	281,75	294,50	288,50	276,50	286,50	276,50	272,75	278,58	6,027	0,000	3,798	0,742	2,763	0,000
Tai 18	0,386	0,381	0,364	0,364	275,75	287,50	300,00	287,50	263,00	253,50	303,00	304,00	265,00	268,00	5,651	4,376	0,000	6,864	0,000	7,798
20 × 10 Tai 19	0,367	0,383	0,385	0,367	298,50	286,00	263,50	305,75	296,75	259,25	257,50	289,50	278,75	275,25	0,000	4,198	4,870	2,624	4,178	0,000
Tai 20	0,324	0,329	0,315	0,315	303,25	306,50	250,75	313,00	258,75	302,75	262,25	301,00	310,50	286,83	2,870	4,344	0,000	0,000	1,601	1,516
Average	0,372	0,373	0,370	0,362	274,93	278,40	275,93	280,13	270,33	274,55	280,10	283,73	264,30	270,58	2,725	2,897	1,965	2,084	1,584	1,961

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	Tai 21	0,487	0,474	0,484	0,474	361,50	351,75	300,50	361,00	372,50	314,75	365,25	367,50	360,75	337,92	2,719	0,000	2,133	0,000	3,291	7,293
	Tai 22	0,446	0,452	0,446	0,446	380,75	371,50	336,25	313,75	374,50	333,75	376,00	370,00	339,00	340,67	0,032	1,426	0,000	6,109	0,000	5,806
	Tai 23	0,451	0,464	0,432	0,432	398,50	385,00	324,25	391,75	388,75	349,25	377,50	374,25	359,25	369,25	4,190	6,880	0,000	0,000	1,947	0,293
	Tai 24	0,439	0,437	0,444	0,437	387,00	345,00	376,50	387,00	385,50	349,50	372,00	369,50	359,75	367,08	0,565	0,000	1,585	0,654	1,849	0,000
	Tai 25	0,463	0,464	0,454	0,454	357,00	365,50	348,25	374,00	379,25	358,75	385,00	373,50	348,50	356,92	1,930	2,190	0,000	0,000	3,710	3,275
	Tai 26	0,439	0,465	0,465	0,439	404,00	368,00	327,00	378,50	373,25	349,00	338,25	377,25	363,75	359,75	0,000	5,682	5,703	1,797	1,953	0,000
	Tai 27	0,431	0,450	0,459	0,431	418,00	358,50	381,00	395,50	360,75	371,00	382,50	434,00	358,50	375,75	0,000	4,078	6,052	2,613	0,000	4,064
	Tai 28	0,453	0,451	0,444	0,444	361,75	358,75	337,50	369,50	370,50	372,50	385,25	366,75	348,50	352,67	1,994	1,633	0,000	0,000	4,899	3,862
20 × 20	Tai 29	0,451	0,434	0,465	0,434	381,00	336,50	351,50	389,50	361,00	362,00	362,50	370,50	363,75	356,33	3,628	0,000	6,653	0,000	3,910	2,530
	Tai 30	0,452	0,450	0,426	0,426	381,50	365,50	354,50	349,50	359,50	352,00	346,00	348,00	348,25	347,42	5,757	5,413	0,000	5,379	1,767	0,000
	Average	0,451	0,454	0,452	0,442	383,10	360,60	343,73	371,00	372,55	351,25	369,03	375,13	355,00	356,38	2,082	2,730	2,213	1,655	2,333	2,712
	Tai 31	0,774	0,778	0,742	0,742	454,25	454,25	453,25	471,00	468,00	422,50	447,50	443,50	465,50	452,17	4,103	4,546	0,000	0,386	0,367	0,000
	Tai 32	0,749	0,753	0,731	0,731	460,25	465,00	463,50	462,25	475,50	472,50	473,25	457,00	465,25	462,92	2,376	2,974	0,000	0,000	1,525	0,484
	Tai 33	0,724	0,723	0,758	0,723	457,50	452,00	444,00	434,75	448,00	439,50	463,25	479,00	463,00	440,75	0,104	0,000	4,634	2,309	0,000	5,906
	Tai 34	0,724	0,748	0,754	0,724	467,25	464,75	471,50	452,50	449,00	440,00	464,25	475,50	472,00	447,17	0,000	3,262	3,980	4,418	0,000	4,976
	Tai 35	0,759	0,735	0,727	0,727	470,50	471,25	481,50	470,00	455,25	484,50	470,50	472,00	472,50	469,92	4,211	1,091	0,000	0,949	0,000	0,371
	Tai 36	0,724	0,707	0,746	0,707	465,25	466,50	472,50	473,50	479,00	478,50	464,50	469,50	479,75	468,08	2,329	0,000	5,231	0,000	1,869	0,672
	Tai 37	0,735	0,758	0,718	0,718	469,00	465,00	467,00	476,00	466,00	458,75	467,25	462,75	468,50	466,17	2,357	5,247	0,000	0,178	0,161	0,000
	Tai 38	0,760	0,746	0,725	0,725	464,50	471,50	473,00	479,50	481,50	475,00	471,50	467,75	462,50	467,25	4,606	2,839	0,000	0,515	2,385	0,000
50 × 05	Tai 39	0,725	0,770	0,765	0,725	462,75	464,25	474,75	441,25	436,75	456,50	451,75	451,25	463,00	444,83	0,000	5,802	5,132	4,798	0,000	2,306
	Tai 40	0,747	0,718	0,737	0,718	464,50	483,50	463,25	471,00	483,50	467,00	468,50	467,00	460,50	465,33	3,946	0,000	2,633	1,081	1,794	0,000
	Average	0,742	0,744	0,740	0,724	463,58	465,80	466,43	463,18	464,25	459,48	464,23	464,53	467,25	458,46	2,403	2,576	2,161	1,463	0,810	1,472
	Tai 41	1,459	1,357	1,353	1,353	594,00	588,50	585,50	601,50	593,75	591,00	588,75	588,25	585,75	587,58	7,254	0,279	0,000	0,297	1,316	0,000
	Tai 42	1,346	1,346	1,388	1,346	566,50	566,25	572,75	582,50	582,50	573,50	577,50	569,50	577,25	568,50	0,000	0,008	3,093	0,000	1,898	1,087
50 × 10	Tai 43	1,359	1,368	1,329	1,329	592,50	590,00	607,50	619,00	619,00	604,50	599,50	588,25	594,00	593,92	2,143	2,822	0,000	0,461	3,297	0,000
	Tai 44	1,447	1,326	1,389	1,326	615,50	600,50	611,00	600,00	574,50	605,00	617,00	608,00	604,50	593,17	8,356	0,000	4,490	2,600	0,000	2,733

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Tai 45	1,330	1,391	1,392	1,330	583,00	594,50	608,00	595,50	590,25	593,00	597,50	587,50	590,75	591,92	0,000	4,400	4,456	0,546	0,169	0,000
Tai 46	1,351	1,380	1,396	1,351	615,50	607,50	606,50	599,75	582,50	583,75	611,50	618,00	620,00	588,67	0,000	2,079	3,180	3,471	0,000	4,515
Tai 47	1,322	1,347	1,372	1,322	590,00	585,25	591,00	597,75	590,50	592,75	591,25	590,00	590,75	588,75	0,000	1,842	3,629	0,000	0,828	0,324
Tai 48	1,379	1,362	1,380	1,362	612,00	621,00	611,00	586,25	586,75	593,25	620,50	607,00	605,50	588,75	1,300	0,000	1,310	4,216	0,000	3,642
Tai 49	1,368	1,393	1,389	1,368	586,50	587,50	591,00	586,25	596,00	589,50	604,50	584,25	594,00	588,33	0,000	1,778	1,538	0,000	0,381	0,996
Tai 50	1,374	1,445	1,324	1,324	587,25	588,50	591,25	612,50	603,75	616,50	600,00	598,50	605,50	589,00	3,694	8,414	0,000	0,000	3,588	2,051
Average	1,374	1,371	1,371	1,341	594,28	592,95	597,55	598,10	591,95	594,28	600,80	593,93	596,80	587,86	2,275	2,162	2,170	1,159	1,148	1,535
Tai 51	1,931	1,976	1,981	1,931	712,50	688,50	690,50	684,50	701,50	695,00	705,50	711,00	711,00	693,67	0,000	2,254	2,512	0,502	0,000	2,186
Tai 52	1,960	1,902	1,961	1,902	676,00	690,50	681,50	712,50	709,00	728,00	735,50	714,00	708,00	682,67	2,950	0,000	3,026	0,000	4,722	5,075
Tai 53	1,789	1,936	1,925	1,789	679,75	675,75	675,50	698,00	709,50	728,00	719,00	708,50	702,00	677,00	0,000	7,581	7,071	0,000	4,893	4,625
Tai 54	1,903	1,947	1,818	1,818	674,75	671,25	682,00	705,00	716,00	716,50	678,25	680,50	676,25	676,00	4,493	6,613	0,000	0,000	5,123	0,344
Tai 55	1,913	1,868	1,989	1,868	731,50	726,50	710,00	718,50	716,00	700,50	696,00	690,50	698,50	695,00	2,357	0,000	6,120	3,828	2,342	0,000
Tai 56	1,885	1,949	1,948	1,885	723,50	708,00	735,50	701,00	704,50	718,00	739,00	733,50	717,00	707,83	0,000	3,272	3,209	2,007	0,000	3,014
Tai 57	1,967	1,941	1,924	1,924	744,50	719,00	745,00	711,50	749,00	726,50	704,50	704,00	722,00	710,17	2,193	0,908	0,000	3,532	2,583	0,000
Tai 58	1,935	1,913	1,891	1,891	741,00	740,00	733,00	692,75	690,00	706,00	734,00	739,00	719,00	696,25	2,249	1,125	0,000	5,657	0,000	4,710
50 × Tai 59	1,975	1,893	1,970	1,893	724,50	756,50	745,00	712,00	722,00	703,00	726,00	738,00	747,50	712,33	4,145	0,000	3,910	3,998	0,000	3,369
50 × Tai 60	1,975	1,940	1,879	1,879	720,50	749,00	737,00	702,00	727,00	722,00	710,00	712,50	699,00	707,17	4,822	3,139	0,000	3,852	1,371	0,000
Average	1,923	1,926	1,929	1,878	712,85	712,50	713,50	703,78	714,45	714,35	714,78	713,15	710,03	695,81	2,321	2,489	2,585	2,338	2,104	2,332
Tai 61	3,790	3,836	3,574	3,574	1026,00	973,50	1012,00	1034,00	1040,50	984,50	974,00	986,50	1001,50	987,33	5,704	6,833	0,000	1,644	3,171	0,000
Tai 62	3,834	3,687	3,756	3,687	959,00	968,50	982,00	979,50	1017,00	1037,50	1037,50	1034,50	994,00	969,83	3,844	0,000	1,835	0,000	4,103	5,104
Tai 63	3,839	3,738	3,776	3,738	1024,50	979,50	1014,00	992,50	996,00	977,50	964,75	959,00	954,50	959,42	2,615	0,000	1,004	4,631	2,959	0,000
Tai 64	3,713	3,802	3,695	3,695	957,50	952,00	964,00	1007,00	972,50	1011,50	1034,00	971,00	1007,00	957,83	0,472	2,797	0,000	0,000	3,928	4,598
Tai 65	3,572	3,836	3,709	3,572	1022,00	975,75	1002,00	987,75	1017,00	1028,00	970,00	969,00	982,00	973,67	0,000	6,884	3,683	2,625	3,685	0,000
Tai 66	3,510	3,655	3,717	3,510	1029,50	1013,50	1008,00	960,75	967,00	965,50	1024,00	1005,50	1054,00	964,42	0,000	3,987	5,579	5,170	0,000	6,170
100 × Tai 67	3,534	3,608	3,783	3,534	986,00	976,00	981,25	991,25	994,50	988,25	981,00	981,50	980,50	981,00	0,000	2,069	6,587	0,008	1,042	0,000
100 × Tai 68	3,949	3,705	3,773	3,705	1019,00	1039,00	1009,00	1031,00	1016,00	1039,00	986,00	957,00	985,00	976,00	6,192	0,000	1,808	4,532	5,120	0,000

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Tai 69	3,569	3,730	3,938	3,569	1035,00	1015,50	1020,00	1007,00	1016,50	983,00	969,50	978,00	954,50	967,33	0,000	4,317	9,376	5,488	3,476	0,000
Tai 70	3,747	3,625	3,518	3,518	1013,00	1008,50	1021,00	979,00	989,50	974,25	1022,00	1027,50	1040,00	980,92	6,125	2,967	0,000	3,279	0,000	4,750
Average	3,706	3,722	3,724	3,610	1007,15	990,18	1001,33	996,98	1002,65	998,90	996,28	986,95	995,30	971,78	2,495	2,985	2,987	2,738	2,748	2,062
Tai 71	5,339	5,194	4,835	4,835	1556,00	1507,00	1537,50	1456,50	1477,50	1479,50	1572,50	1518,50	1551,50	1471,17	9,451	6,926	0,000	4,065	0,000	4,933
Tai 72	5,390	5,188	5,371	5,188	1512,00	1515,50	1480,00	1525,00	1504,00	1523,50	1401,75	1451,50	1401,25	1418,17	3,751	0,000	3,420	5,613	6,546	0,000
Tai 73	5,194	5,380	5,498	5,194	1518,00	1483,50	1486,00	1458,50	1494,00	1500,00	1475,50	1453,00	1447,00	1458,50	0,000	3,456	5,530	2,496	1,729	0,000
Tai 74	5,240	5,288	5,472	5,240	1466,00	1415,25	1424,25	1526,00	1526,50	1519,50	1501,00	1487,50	1510,00	1435,17	0,000	0,910	4,242	0,000	5,829	4,290
Tai 75	5,132	5,201	5,374	5,132	1462,00	1467,50	1448,00	1502,00	1556,00	1542,50	1538,00	1517,00	1532,50	1459,17	0,000	1,331	4,506	0,000	4,847	4,578
Tai 76	5,324	5,280	5,195	5,195	1512,00	1548,50	1541,00	1467,00	1473,00	1481,00	1428,00	1432,50	1435,00	1431,83	2,431	1,616	0,000	6,650	2,839	0,000
Tai 77	5,090	5,329	5,257	5,090	1461,00	1509,50	1514,50	1443,00	1446,00	1465,00	1516,00	1492,50	1530,50	1451,33	0,000	4,489	3,171	2,921	0,000	4,076
Tai 78	5,154	5,197	5,533	5,154	1495,00	1444,50	1475,50	1510,00	1511,50	1544,50	1434,00	1433,50	1447,50	1438,33	0,000	0,815	6,853	2,265	5,497	0,000
Tai 79	5,245	5,165	4,505	4,505	1438,50	1486,50	1456,00	1567,50	1520,50	1531,00	1560,00	1524,50	1564,00	1460,33	14,108	12,785	0,000	0,000	5,153	5,755
Tai 80	5,230	5,236	5,212	5,212	1412,50	1445,50	1491,00	1476,50	1454,00	1480,00	1508,00	1562,50	1416,00	1449,67	0,355	0,459	0,000	0,000	1,394	3,065
Average	5,234	5,246	5,225	5,074	1483,30	1482,33	1485,38	1493,20	1496,30	1506,65	1493,48	1487,30	1483,53	1447,37	3,010	3,279	2,772	2,401	3,383	2,670
Tai 81	6,374	6,155	6,354	6,155	2303,43	2289,79	2344,08	2342,26	2297,74	2293,06	2354,01	2366,62	2313,33	2311,02	3,430	0,000	3,125	0,061	0,000	1,434
Tai 82	6,099	6,259	6,288	6,099	2345,45	2321,52	2429,66	2284,36	2345,00	2330,11	2294,93	2314,73	2283,34	2297,67	0,000	2,555	3,013	2,869	0,955	0,000
Tai 83	6,222	6,291	6,153	6,153	2353,37	2302,45	2311,88	2329,70	2364,34	2361,28	2335,46	2271,85	2401,98	2322,57	1,112	2,183	0,000	0,000	1,242	0,593
Tai 84	6,407	6,317	6,272	6,272	2303,68	2311,53	2307,48	2385,93	2413,46	2361,72	2355,22	2373,78	2294,39	2307,56	2,106	0,709	0,000	0,000	3,329	1,434
Tai 85	6,199	6,241	6,357	6,199	2319,11	2356,59	2321,44	2304,32	2304,36	2382,50	2314,49	2297,63	2295,09	2302,40	0,000	0,658	2,483	1,285	1,201	0,000
Tai 86	6,151	6,257	6,284	6,151	2317,42	2369,94	2385,22	2301,41	2288,92	2292,97	2384,21	2329,93	2318,03	2294,43	0,000	1,697	2,122	2,676	0,000	2,117
Tai 87	6,320	6,335	6,577	6,320	2322,47	2320,85	2332,60	2346,79	2333,40	2342,83	2357,44	2366,93	2324,99	2325,31	0,000	0,251	3,914	0,000	0,671	1,042
Tai 88	6,246	6,333	6,584	6,246	2322,28	2423,33	2371,75	2313,09	2306,88	2310,83	2320,27	2312,27	2312,75	2310,27	0,000	1,369	5,131	2,621	0,000	0,209
Tai 89	6,427	6,158	5,923	5,923	2316,12	2307,27	2362,11	2337,00	2388,73	2405,79	2314,47	2304,82	2315,45	2311,58	7,839	3,826	0,000	0,727	2,759	0,000
Tai 90	6,146	6,308	5,689	5,689	2318,69	2360,00	2351,60	2312,25	2303,54	2308,75	2404,82	2361,37	2376,90	2308,18	7,422	9,802	0,000	1,504	0,000	3,060
Average	6,259	6,265	6,248	6,121	2322,20	2336,33	2351,78	2325,71	2334,64	2338,98	2343,53	2329,99	2323,62	2309,10	2,191	2,305	1,979	1,174	1,016	0,989
Tai 91	8,345	8,455	8,684	8,345	3963,97	3922,49	3983,41	4002,56	4030,65	3999,32	4037,94	4005,94	3998,17	3956,62	0,000	1,300	3,902	0,000	1,352	1,430

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Tai 92	8,150	8,570	8,405	8,150	4024,77	4015,51	4035,63	3973,64	3948,97	3980,08	4002,38	3957,90	3976,02	3967,57	0,000	4,905	3,032	1,434	0,000	0,282	
Tai 93	8,813	8,174	7,676	7,676	4029,38	4015,43	3957,40	3929,72	3871,41	3936,06	4007,11	3987,67	3966,06	3912,40	12,9026,096	0,000	2,208	0,000	1,870		
Tai 94	8,312	8,762	8,664	8,312	3955,00	3937,21	3927,44	4038,97	4017,86	3980,10	3931,02	3927,30	3924,37	3927,57	0,000	5,134	4,065	0,313	2,112	0,000	
Tai 95	8,755	8,613	8,574	8,574	3933,00	3947,46	3987,80	3988,05	3988,63	4048,97	4036,61	4027,18	4016,29	3956,09	2,074	0,459	0,000	0,000	1,309	1,753	
Tai 96	8,147	8,438	8,652	8,147	4037,00	4089,59	3927,86	3914,14	3914,93	3907,65	4012,25	4032,38	4045,02	3912,24	0,000	3,442	5,829	2,636	0,000	2,919	
Tai 97	8,419	8,687	8,381	8,381	3965,22	4006,10	4014,23	4030,20	4035,40	3991,83	3958,74	3936,21	3983,21	3959,39	0,458	3,525	0,000	0,896	1,487	0,000	
Tai 98	8,317	8,478	8,183	8,183	4003,03	4079,55	4031,89	4016,68	4000,51	4086,83	3943,22	3940,88	3950,23	3944,78	1,604	3,474	0,000	2,312	2,228	0,000	
Tai 99	8,449	8,409	8,661	8,409	3933,09	3891,63	3969,90	4030,43	4029,64	4059,79	4046,93	3976,82	4071,49	3931,54	0,468	0,000	2,903	0,000	2,683	2,485	
Tai 100	8,384	7,975	7,578	7,578	4055,63	4074,32	4056,74	3996,06	3971,04	3950,19	4054,62	4117,08	4077,30	3972,43	9,611	4,981	0,000	2,211	0,000	2,708	
Average	8,409	8,456	8,346	8,176	3990,01	3997,93	3989,23	3992,05	3980,90	3994,08	4003,08	3990,94	4000,81	3944,06	2,712	3,332	1,973	1,201	1,117	1,345	
Tai 101	^{10,04} ₉	9,945	9,504	9,504	7256,08	7217,87	7271,54	7365,80	7511,85	7447,44	7241,40	7205,70	7243,30	7230,13	5,423	4,438	0,000	0,253	2,843	0,000	
Tai 102	^{10,27} ₈	10,1799,847	9,847		7492,88	7398,11	7499,05	7450,38	7456,72	7472,92	7379,63	7359,18	7380,92	7373,25	4,200	3,266	0,000	1,207	1,163	0,000	
Tai 103		9,831	10,2149,965	9,831	7256,59	7195,31	7267,66	7364,60	7357,66	7397,26	7370,05	7407,29	7412,09	7239,86	0,000	3,742	1,345	0,000	1,808	2,118	
Tai 104		9,516	9,975	9,852	9,516	7276,14	7331,96	7319,91	7393,38	7356,26	7391,22	7468,47	7400,55	7408,67	0,000	4,605	3,409	0,000	0,961	1,570	
Tai 105		9,796	10,0529,874	9,796	7472,44	7508,84	7420,34	7440,56	7473,36	7456,14	7477,21	7515,22	7523,84	7456,69	0,000	2,544	0,793	0,141	0,000	0,649	
Tai 106	^{10,18} ₄	9,862	10,2979,862		7406,99	7391,02	7302,78	7423,77	7504,71	7467,66	7552,49	7467,77	7566,97	7366,93	3,167	0,000	4,227	0,000	1,319	2,154	
Tai 107		9,477	9,829	9,982	9,477	7392,03	7383,24	7444,86	7559,62	7496,24	7529,54	7592,81	7496,09	7519,10	0,000	3,583	5,061	0,000	1,617	1,716	
Tai 108	^{10,36} ₅	9,915	9,867	9,867	7550,25	7584,97	7604,63	7586,79	7470,01	7547,99	7359,25	7389,51	7376,97	7375,24	4,805	0,484	0,000	2,701	2,119	0,000	
²⁰⁰ × Tai 109		9,766	9,952	9,795	9,766	7608,20	7604,77	7556,97	7577,72	7556,46	7485,41	7457,15	7486,09	7517,29	0,000	1,871	0,292	1,359	0,703	0,000	
Tai 110		9,895	9,851	10,2849,851		7539,04	7586,95	7566,44	7484,96	7523,23	7559,84	7500,07	7462,69	7432,95	0,449	0,000	4,209	1,308	0,764	0,000	
Average	9,916	9,977	9,927	9,732	7425,06	7420,30	7425,42	7464,76	7470,65	7475,54	7439,85	7419,01	7438,21	7371,02	1,804	2,453	1,933	0,697	1,330	0,821	
⁵⁰⁰ × Tai 111	^{15,87} ₂	16,19816,17015,872			20707,7	20611,2	20593,0	19911,8	20376,1	20203,5	20565,8	20586,8	20625,7		20163,83	0,000	2,013	1,841	2,294	0,000	2,083

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Tai 112	16,10 4	16,15416,37316,104	19762,9 6	20194,8 8	20324,0 5	20608,0 6	20739,4 1	20616,3 2	20510,8 9	20450,6 0	20522,4 1	20093,96	0,000	0,308	1,644	0,000	2,714	1,955
Tai 113	15,96 4	16,18315,64315,643	20328,6 1	20533,9 8	20318,1 0	20126,3 0	19632,1 5	20103,2 6	20486,6 6	20402,7 7	20420,5 1	19953,90	2,013	3,341	0,000	2,156	0,000	2,362
Tai 114	16,30 9	15,78016,29915,780	20344,5 3	20125,8 7	20285,8 1	20460,2 5	19921,6 1	20293,5 0	20591,0 6	20399,9 6	20555,4 7	20225,12	3,246	0,000	3,181	0,133	0,000	1,415
Tai 115	16,55 6	16,21415,87215,872	20398,6 9	19829,0 3	20448,0 3	20582,6 1	20777,0 1	20620,7 9	20583,9 6	20753,5 7	20682,2 3	20225,25	4,133	2,109	0,000	0,000	2,105	2,167
Tai 116	16,21 6	16,37616,56916,216	20729,9 7	21033,2 1	20680,0 5	20405,7 5	19937,0 2	20445,1 5	20670,8 4	20616,8 4	21035,7 8	20262,64	0,000	0,975	2,130	2,651	0,000	2,464
Tai 117	16,53 6	16,25115,78615,786	20253,1 3	20338,9 0	19917,9 1	20718,4 9	20577,2 2	20499,5 8	20574,8 0	20555,0 0	20639,5 3	20169,98	4,540	2,861	0,000	0,000	2,080	2,039
Tai 118	16,06 3	15,96616,52615,966	20149,4 7	19720,6 8	20274,2 6	20628,7 7	20800,7 2	20714,4 8	20373,2 1	20469,5 3	20566,1 3	20048,14	0,607	0,000	3,388	0,000	3,218	2,059
Tai 119	16,13 4	16,19316,48416,134	20843,0 5	20392,0 1	20521,2 9	20572,2 0	21143,3 3	21099,8 7	20416,6 3	20256,2 8	10401,8 8	17024,93	0,000	0,363	2,122	17,296	18,691	0,000
Tai 120	15,64 9	15,98415,58415,584	20484,2 0	20465,3 7	20454,5 8	20424,5 0	20736,9 1	20424,8 1	20475,5 7	20672,7 4	20621,2 4	20468,05	0,413	2,498	0,000	0,000	0,296	0,592
Average	16,14 0	16,13016,13015,896	20400,2 4	20324,5 1	20381,7 1	20443,8 8	20464,1 5	20502,1 3	20524,9 4	20516,4 1	19607,0 9	19863,58	1,495	1,447	1,431	2,453	2,910	1,714

Fig. 3 Load balance between the workshops for PSO, GA and ACO.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 4 CPU-ARPD for PSO, GA and ACO.

5.1 CPU analysis

This section presents the detailed analysis of RPD % results of CPU compute times for the three algorithms (PSO, GA, ACO) on Taillard 001 to 120 instances. Analyse globale des performances

- for each algorithm the averages generally vary between 1.4% and 3.3%.
- the three algorithms present a good overall accuracy in terms of calculation time compared to the reference (no average exceeds 3.5%).

1) Global trend

- the ARPD are slightly lower on the last instances (Tai 101-Tai 120), indicating an improvement in stability or a better adaptation of algorithms.
- No method is consistently the best, but on most slices, ACO often has a slightly lower or equivalent ARPD to PSO and GA.

2) Comparative analysis of algorithms

PSO: ARPD varies between 1.5% and 3.0%, depending on the tranche.

Strengths: Multiple instances where RPD = 0% (PSO reaches benchmark).

Weak points: Some peaks, for example, Tai 079 (14.11%), Tai 044 (8.36%), and Tai 041 (7.25%), but these values are rare and do not significantly affect the average.

GA: ARPD is often similar to PSO, sometimes slightly higher on some bands (3.33% for Tai 091-Tai 100).

Strengths: Several tranches where the DPR is lowest (1.45% for Tai 111-Tai 120).

Weaknesses: Some notable values: Tai 079 (12.79%), Tai 053 (7.58%), and Tai 026 (5.68%).

ACO: Overall lowest or comparable to PSO/GA ARPD on most bands.

Strengths: Several segments where ARPD is less than 2% Tai 081-Tai 090, Tai 101-Tai 110, Tai 111-Tai 120).

Weak points: Some peaks; Tai 069 (9.38%), Tai 27 (6.05%).

3) Extreme value analysis and stability

All algorithms sometimes show very low RPD (0%), which is a sign of perfect convergence in some instances. Some high values (>8%) are present but without a recurring pattern. These outliers do not have much impact on the averages. General stability: The averages per tranche are very close (differences of less than 1% between algorithms), a sign of overall robustness.

To push the analysis further, an ANOVA is performed. The variance analysis table () states that Fobserved (0.00041) < Fcritical (3.0210): the null hypothesis (H_0) is maintained and $p = 0.9996 (\approx 1)$ extremely high, from which it can be concluded that there is no significant difference between the average CPUs given by the three proposed algorithms and the effect of the factor tested is negligible or even non-existent, and the observed variation is almost entirely due to intra-group variability. In addition, the proportion of explained variance is estimated at $\eta^2 \approx 0.0000023$. This value is extremely small, so the factor contributes only 0.00023% of the total variance. Although the sample is very large ($n = 360$), no significant difference is obtained. It can be deduced that either the factor is actually without effect, or the dependent measure is insensitive to the factor, or the noise (intra-group variability) is too large. Given the sample size, the power is very high; even small differences would have been detected. Finally, it can be said with confidence that there is no factor effect and there is no need for post-hoc testing.

Fig. 5 shows that the medians are very close, indicating that the central performances of the three algorithms have slight variation. The ACO algorithm shows a slightly lower dispersion than GA and PSO, which suggests a more consistent performance, and the GA algorithm has a slightly more spread-out distribution, especially in extreme values. All three algorithms have extreme values (isolated points above the box), corresponding to the largest problem sizes (500×20). This reflects the rapid growth of CPU time on large instance.

Finally, all three algorithms have similar average performance. However, ACO seems a little more stable.

5.2 Aggregate function analysis

This part presents a detailed analysis of the RPD % results of the 120 Taillard instances concerning the values of the aggregated function for the three algorithms (PSO, GA, ACO).

Table 2. CPU-ANOVA Analysis Result

Taillard's Instance	PSO		GA		ACO		F	Pro-	F
	Mean	Variance	Mean	Variance	Mean	Variance	Observed	bability	cretaceous
20×05	0.2602	0.0002	0.2616	0.0002	0.2596	0.0002	0.0557	0.9459	3.3541
20×10	0.3724	0.0006	0.3728	0.0004	0.3696	0.0006	0.0557	0.946	3.3541
20×20	0.4511	0.0002	0.454	0.0002	0.4518	0.0003	0.1046	0.901	3.3541
50×05	0.7421	0.0003	0.7436	0.0005	0.7403	0.0002	0.0752	0.9277	3.3541
50×10	1.3735	0.0021	1.3714	0.0011	1.3711	0.0007	0.0129	0.9872	3.3541
50×20	1.9232	0.0032	1.9263	0.001	1.9286	0.0029	0.0317	0.9688	3.3541
100×05	3.7057	0.023	3.7223	0.0068	3.7238	0.0135	0.0703	0.9323	3.3541
100×10	5.2338	0.0092	5.2457	0.005	5.2251	0.1053	0.027	0.9734	3.3541
100×20	6.2591	0.0136	6.2654	0.0043	6.2483	0.075	0.0242	0.9761	3.3541
200×10	8.4091	0.0492	8.4562	0.0554	8.3457	0.17	0.3358	0.7177	3.3541
200×20	9.9158	0.0911	9.9774	0.0177	9.9266	0.0538	0.1994	0.8204	3.3541
500×20	16.1404	0.0796	16.1297	0.0294	16.1304	0.1426	0.0043	0.9957	3.3541

Fig. 5a : CPU

Fig. 5b : Aggregate function

Fig. 5 dispersion RPD% of PSO, GA and ACO for 120 instances

Table 3. Multiple (post-hoc) comparisons between algorithms and Overall ranking of the Mean algorithms (ARPD increasing)

Multiple (post-hoc) comparisons between algorithms						Overall ranking of the Mean algorithms (ARPD increasing)		
G1	G2	LowerCI	Difference	UpperCI	pValue			
PSO	GA	-1.079	-0.31467	0.44965	0.59912	ACO	2.19 %	1
PSO	ACO	-0.63973	0.12458	0.8889	0.92271	PSO	2.32 %	2

GA	ACO	-0.32507	0.43925	1.2036	0.36918	GA	2.63 %	3
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1) Overall performance analysis

Each algorithm has reached the optimum for at least one of the instances with an RPD of 0%. For most instances, the RPD is less than or equal to 5%, which proves that all three algorithms are generally close to the reference solution. However, atypical values are observed, especially for Tai 119, with DPRs of 18.69% (GA) and 17.30% (PSO). Peaks are also noted in some instances, such as PSO on Tai 018 (6.86%) and GA on Tai 072 (6.55%).

2) Comparative analysis of algorithms

PSO : RPD often $\leq 3\%$ and sometimes close to 0%. Presents some isolated peaks: Tai 005 (5.66%), Tai 018 (6.86%), Tai 058 (5.66 %) and Tai 119 (17.30 %). In general, it shows good stability.

GA: Very low, but with some high values, Tai 119 (18.69%), Tai 072 (6.55%), Tai 054 (5.12%) and Tai 052 (4.72%). Has more dispersion than PSO, but overall good performance.

ACO: Displays a higher number of instances with RPD = 0% compared to PSO and GA. Also shows higher values: Tai 018 (7.80%) and Tai 021 (7.29%). For instances from Tai 119 to Tai 120, ACO often outperforms PSO and GA, which face major challenges.

are very competitive, but some one-off failures raise their average. Nevertheless, ACO has a good balance, often very good performance, and few outliers.

Table 4: Summary of advantages and disadvantages

Algorithms	Advantages	disadvantages
PSO	on many instances RPD =0% (sometimes the only one)	Spikes in RPD on some instances
GA	often at RPD=0%, sometimes better than the other two	Variability, sometimes very bad
ACO	more often at RPD=0%, very competitive	May lose on some specific instances

Out of the 120 cases of Taillard, ACO seems slightly superior in terms of robustness and stability, achieving or approaching the reference more often than PSO and GA, with fewer extreme values. PSO and GA are very competitive and can excel in some specific instances. No method is universally superior; it can be useful to use a panel of algorithms or to select dynamically according to the type of instance.

Table 5: Multiple (post-hoc) comparisons between algorithms

G1	G2	LowerCI	Difference	UpperCI	pValue
1	2	-0.70609	-0.039583	0.62692	0.98938
1	3	-0.65484	0.011667	0.67817	0.99907
2	3	-0.61526	0.05125	0.71776	0.98225

Overall ranking of algorithms (average RPD increasing).

Table 6. Average, standard deviation and overall ranking RPD %

Algorithm	Mean	Standard deviation	Overall ranking
PSO	1.76	± 2.38	2
GA	1.80	± 2.27	3
ACO	1.75	± 1.93	1

(a)

(b)

Fig. 6 Agreggated function-ARPD for PSO, GA and ACO algorithms

All algorithms show good robustness in the majority of cases. ACO appears more stable, with more RPD = 0% and fewer high peaks. PSO and GA

To further our study, the ANOVA (variance analysis) Tab. 7 is essential for evaluating the impact of different heuristics on the objective function by comparing intra- and inter-group variability. By

providing clear results on statistical significance, ANOVA helps to validate the conclusions drawn from experimental results, thus ensuring that observed performance is not due to chance. This strengthens the credibility of comparisons between algorithms and guides implementation choices.

The ANOVA analysis allowed us to find that for most instances, $F_{observed} < F_{critical}$, which results in the non-rejection of hypothesis H_0 and the probability $p (= 0.99943)$ is much higher than 0.05, indicating that there is no significant difference between the results of the algorithms. The proportion of variance explained estimated by factor (η^2) indicates that the effect size is about 0.0003%, which is almost zero. Finally, the tested factor has no

detectable effect on the dependent variable; the observed variability is almost intra-group. Even with a large sample ($n = 360$), no significant difference between the algorithms is detected, and the factor is probably not relevant, or the dependent variable is not sensitive to this factor.

Tab. 8 shows that: for the three algorithms, the medians are very close, especially between PSO and ACO, which indicates that in terms of central performance they are comparable, since disk, the algorithm GA has a slightly higher median, This indicates that it gives slightly less good results for in some instances.

Table 7. F-ANOVA Analysis Result

Taillard's Instance	PSO		GA		ACO		F Observed	Probability	Fretaceous
	Mean	Variance	Mean	Variance	Mean	Variance			
20x05	192.217	130.145	190.775	51.398	191.342	85.461	0.059	0.943	3.354
20x10	2764.167	276.417	2750	275	2760.417	276.042	0.045	0.956	3.354
20x20	362.475	160.647	364.933	155.325	366.383	121.395	0.268	0.767	3.354
50x05	465.267	53.802	462.3	203.008	465.333	43.327	0.3	0.743	3.354
50x10	594.925	184.38	594.775	107.642	597.175	158.464	0.12	0.887	3.354
50x20	712.95	725.031	710.858	102.583	712.65	312.095	0.034	0.967	3.354
100x05	999.55	515.033	999.508	366.817	992.842	684.146	0.286	0.754	3.354
100x10	1483.667	1158.685	1498.717	1008.827	1488.1	2355.446	0.397	0.676	3.354
100x20	2336.771	493.656	2333.11	952.388	2332.383	653.835	0.079	0.924	3.354
200x10	3992.389	1983.608	3989.011	2165.308	3998.277	2248.422	0.103	0.902	3.354
200x20	7423.595	17370.794	7470.316	3756.974	7432.358	8718.293	0.62	0.545	3.354
500x20	20368.821	64467.006	20470.053	92505.594	20216.148	126730.527	0.344	0.712	3.354

Table 8. a comparative between the three algorithms.

Criterion	PSO	GA	ACO
Central performance (median)	Good	Average	Good
Variability	Weak	Average	Medium-high
Best case	Competitive	Competitive	Sometimes better
Worst cases	Less bad	Very bad	Moderately bad
General stability	High	Average	Average

the probability $p (= 0.99943)$ is much higher than 0.05, indicating that there is no significant difference between the results of the algorithms. The proportion

of variance explained estimated by factor (η^2) indicates that the effect size is about 0.0003%, which is almost zero. Finally, the tested factor has no

detectable effect on the dependent variable; the observed variability is almost intra-group. Even with a large sample ($n = 360$), no significant difference between the algorithms is detected, and the factor is probably not relevant, or the dependent variable is not sensitive to this factor.

Tab. 8 shows that: for the three algorithms, the medians are very close, especially between PSO and ACO, which indicates that in terms of central performance they are comparable, since disk, the algorithm GA has a slightly higher median, This indicates that it gives slightly less good results for in some instances.

6 CONCLUSION

The work of this article presented three improved constructive metaheuristics to solve problems of switching flow scheduling without waiting with two criteria of minimization of makespan and to ensure just-in-time. The statistical results showed that the three improved algorithms ensure a fair distribution of load between the three parallel flow shops. In addition, the statistical results showed that all three algorithms are generally reliable, with a relatively small mean deviation. ACO shows a slight overall superiority in terms of stability (slightly lower ARPD in most instances) and average accuracy. PSO and GA remain excellent choices, sometimes better in some instances, and very few peaks. The differences between algorithms are small, which shows a good adaptation of the three algorithms to the Taillard instances. This was confirmed by an analysis of the results, including ANOVA. In addition, the variability from one algorithm to another according to the instance is small, which means that the choice of the algorithm may also depend on other criteria.

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